

Expert Interview Guide – mHealth Design Recommendations in Indonesia

1. Opening

Thank you for taking the time to participate. I am [Researcher Name] from [Institution]. This study analyses hundreds of thousands of user reviews from Indonesian mHealth apps. From this analysis, we developed a series of design recommendations to improve reliability, inclusivity, and trust in digital health applications. This interview aims to obtain your expert insights to validate, refine, or prioritise these recommendations. The discussion will last about 20–30 minutes. With your permission, this session will be recorded for research purposes (anonymised).

2. Respondent Background

1. Briefly tell us about your background and role in digital health or mHealth development.
2. How would you describe the current state of mHealth in Indonesia (opportunities, challenges, regulations, and user behaviour)?

A. Payments (Reliability and Transparency)

Many users report failed transactions, slow refunds, and auto-debit without consent. We recommend better transaction validation, automated refund mechanisms, and more flexible payment options.

1. What is your view on these payment issues in practice?
2. Are the proposed recommendations realistic for the Indonesian context?
3. What additional steps can improve user trust in digital payment systems?

B. Privacy (Data Protection and User Trust)

Users fear data leaks and misuse of personal contact information. We suggest end-to-end encryption, restricted third-party access, and verified communication channels.

1. How do you assess current privacy compliance among Indonesian mHealth apps?
2. What are the biggest challenges for developers to implement strong privacy measures?

3. What contextual approaches (policy, user education, UI design) could strengthen these recommendations?

C. Doctor Consultation (Quality and Responsiveness)

Users report long waiting times and overly generic doctor responses. We recommend implementing queue estimation, auto-monitoring for inactive sessions, and consultation quality guidelines.

1. Are these recommendations feasible given operational realities in Indonesia?
2. How can consultation quality be maintained without overburdening doctors?
3. What indicators should be used to measure consultation performance?

D. Connectivity & Resources (Efficiency and Accessibility)

Many users experience app slowness despite stable internet and complain about large app size. We recommend server optimisation, data caching, and efficient resource usage.

1. How important are efficiency and connectivity for mHealth adoption in low-resource settings?
2. Do these technical strategies sufficiently address Indonesia's infrastructure realities?
3. Are there supporting policies or partnerships that can help developers optimise app performance?

E. Updates & Stability (System Reliability)

Users complain about new bugs after updates. We recommend regression testing and planned update cycles with clear user benefits.

1. How feasible is regression testing for Indonesian app developers?
2. What strategies can balance innovation speed with system stability?

F. BPJS & Administration (Integration with Health Systems)

Users still need to attend BPJS offices despite the digital app. We recommend real-time integration among BPJS, faskes, and hospital systems.

1. How realistic is full digital integration in Indonesia?
 2. What are the key steps for efficient and inclusive BPJS digitalisation?
 3. Are there successful cases or models Indonesia could adopt?Notes:
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G. Advertising & Notification (User Experience and Monetisation)

Users complain about intrusive ads and unreliable notifications. We recommend limiting ad frequency, using lightweight ads, and enabling multi-channel notifications (SMS, email, WhatsApp).

1. How can developers balance monetisation with user comfort?
2. Is WhatsApp a suitable and secure channel for notifications in health apps?

4. Reflection & Prioritisation

1. From all these recommendations, which three aspects do you consider the most urgent to improve in Indonesian mHealth?
2. Are there any recommendations that are less relevant or impractical at this stage?
3. Is there any important aspect not covered that should be included?

5. Closing

Thank you very much for your time and insights. Your input will help refine the final set of design recommendations for Indonesian mHealth applications. We will be happy to share a summary of findings once the study is complete.